

SPECTRAL ANALYSIS OF AEROMAGNETIC DATA OVER LONGUDA PLATEAU AND ENVIRONS, NORTH-EASTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The investigation involve the analysis of lineraments and spectral analysis of total - intensity magnetic field data over the Longuda Plateau and environs, Guyuk area. The total magnetic field map exhibit direction of NE-SW and E-W lineraments. The NE-SW lineraments coincide with Longuda basalts while the E-W coincide with the Yola arm of Benue Trough. Result from spectral analysis of the aeromagnetic data indicate two depth source model. The depth to deeper magnetic sources ranges from 1900m to 2620m and could be identified with the basement. The shallow magnetic source ranges from 512m to 670m this could be attributed to near surface intrusive. And laying river valleys in the study area. The results obtained from the study compared favorably with that from Gravity studies.

KEYWORDS: Basement, Benue Trough, Magnetic field, Basalts, lineaments and intrusive.

INTRODUCTION

The study area is located between longitude 11 °30' and 12° 00'IE and latitude 9°30' and 10°00' N in North-Eastern Nigeria (Fig.1). It lies in the Guyuk sheet within the cretaceous Benue trough. The area is predominately hilly as the name implies and is drained mainly by the Benue and Gongola rivers. Airborne magnetic surveys provide a quick means of geological mapping. The magnetic data give information about geological patterns at depth about the metamorphic basement on which younger sedimentary rock lie, and trough light on the presence of major structures which may have influenced its development.

The present work is an attempt to analyze aeromagnetic data over Longuda Plateau, Guyuk area which believes will contribute a better understanding of the geology of the area.

GEOLOGICAL SETTINGS

Geological studies in the Benue trough have been widely reported in literature by Gtatchley and Jones, 1965, Burke *et al* 1970; Carter *et al*, 1963; Offodile, 1976; Osazuwa *et al* 1981 and Offegbu 1985.

The earliest documented sediment deposition in the area was in aptain-ALbian period when fluviclastic sediments of Bima formation were laid unconformably on the basement in the fitted wrench fault basin. The structural deformation which later caused the basin to sag, led to the development of a trough which allowed the upper cretaceous Marine deposition. This transgressive episode led to the deposition of Yolde, Dukul, Jessu, Sekule and Numanha sedimentary formation, all these formation flanks the younger basalts of Longuda plateau. These sediments outcrops as inliers to Bima formation in Dadiya syncline (Fig. 1) The lithofacies consist of the continental arenaceous Bima formation believed to be braided stream sediments (Braide, 1982). This formation is the single largest occuimg lithofacies in the area, found NW, SW and NE ward.

The Yolde formation outcrops in places such as Bamban, Yolde, North West of Galengu. The Dukul, Jessu, Sekule and Numanha formation are shallow marine depositions of limestone, shale and mudstone and they are found mainly as narrow strips of rocks in the study area, such as at Banju Guyuk etc. continental conditions followed the marine and resulted in the deposition of Lamja formation which consist of sand stone, coal, shale and limestone. The Longuda Basalt of tertiary age terminates the lithological succession in the area. The basalts covers approximately 160km² and is located centrally in the area, these Longuda basalt is flanked by the cretaceous sediments of the Benue trough in the study area. The basalts extends in the NW -SE direction with a minor arm extending SW towards Bambam town. It is an olivine rich basalt of fine grained texture. River Valley alluvium is confined to the

banks of the Benue and Gongola rivers. Sediments in the area were subjected to tectonism before the tertiary resulting in the existence of folds and faults, prominent among the folds are the Lamurde anticline and the Dadiya syncline south western part of the study area. The faults are found in the NW and NE part of the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Contoured aeromagnetic data over the Longuda Plateau, Guyuk area have been compiled by the geological survey of Nigeria (GSN) (Fig.2) as part of the Nigeria wide geological survey data. The data were acquired along a series of NE-SW with a flight line spacing of 2km, average flight elevation of 150m above terrain and a nominal tie line spacing of 20km. The geomagnetic gradient was removed using the international geomagnetic reference field formula (IGRF). The map is published on the scale of 1:1000

Fig 1: Geological Map of study area (Adapted From Carter et al, 1963)

The magnetic data were also subjected to 2-D spectral analysis for depth estimates to their sources. 2-D technique for spectral analysis of magnetic anomalies has been described by several authors (Bhattacharyya, 1966, Spector and Grant 1970, Cornard *et al* 1983, Nur *et al*, 1994). For the analysis of this data, the mathematical formulation of Nur *et al* 1994 were used.

Given a residual magnetic anomaly map of dimension L x L, digitized at equal intervals, the residual total intensity anomaly values can be expressed in terms of a double Fourier series expansion; N,M

$$T(X,Y) = \sum \sum P_m^n \cos\left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}\right)(nx + my)\right] + Q_m^n \sin\left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}\right)(nx + my)\right] \quad (1)$$

Where L=Length of the square side, P_m^n and Q_m^n =Fourier amplitudes and N, M =Number of grid points along X, Y directions .

$$P_m^n \cos\left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}\right)(nx + my)\right] + Q_m^n \sin\left[\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}\right)(nx + my)\right] \quad (2)$$

Represent a partial wave for which

$$(P_m^n)^2 + (Q_m^n)^2 = (C_m^n)^2 \quad (3)$$

C_m^n is the amplitude of the partial wave while the frequency of this wave is given as

$$f_m^n = (n^2 + m^2)^{1/2}$$

The Fourier transformation of a section of magnetic survey digitized in a square grid therefore forms a rectangular matrix of coefficient which can be reduced to a set of average amplitudes dependent only on the frequency (Hann *et ai*, 1976).

These average amplitude fully represent a spectrum form which the depth to magnetic sources can be estimated. To carry out spectral analysis, the area under study was divided into blocks of 16 x 16 data points making sure that as much as possible, the essential part of an anomaly contains more than one maximum or minimum. The data for each block was subjected to 2-D Fourier transformation.

Fig.2: Total intensity aeromagnetic map of Guyuk area (for absolute values add 32,000 gammas)

The average amplitude Spectrum all waves falling within a given frequency range is then computed by summing the Fourier amplitudes and dividing by the sum of the number of frequencies. These average amplitudes are then plotted against the frequency on a semi-log scale. Straight lines of best fits are drawn through the different segments of the spectrum. The depths to the magnetic source are related to the slopes of the lines segment by the relation.

$$Z = \frac{SL}{2\pi}$$

Where S=slope, L=length of square side (Negi *et al* 1983). The depth estimate for four blocks that covers the study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Depth of magnetic sources obtained for Longuda plateau and environs

Block 1 D ₁ =1900m D ₂ =546m	Block 3 D ₁ =2620m D ₂ =552m
Block 2 D ₁ =1972m D ₂ =512m	Block 4 D ₁ =670m D ₂ =647m

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Generally, there would always be a magnetic susceptibility contrast across a fracture zone due to oxidation of magnetic to hematite, and / or infilling of fracture planes by dyke like bodies, whose magnetic susceptibilities are different from those of their host rocks. Such geological features may appear as thin elliptical closures or nosing on an aeromagnetic map. Bearing this in mind, prominent elliptical closures and nosing of contours were identified on the magnetic map. These features represent geological lineaments. Their positions are indicated by lines drawn parallel to the elongation and through the center of the anomalies and they are presented in Fig.3. The main trend of the lineaments is NE-SW with a subordinate E-W trend.

Aeromagnetic anomalies over the study area consist of slow to fast varying types. The NE-SW lineament is a concentrated sequence restricted to the plateau central zone of the area and coincident with the Longuda Basalt flow (Fig.3), while the E-W occupies the broader part of the area and coincident with the sedimentary cover. Few other rapid varying anomalies exist particularly in the SW of the area and they are probably caused by basic intrusives within the sedimentary rocks.

The magnetic lineaments of Fig.3 are mainly attributed to Precambrian basement fractures which were initiated prior to the formation of the Benue trough (Osazuwa *et al*, 1981). Their relative concentration between Guyuk and Cham, and between Bangu and Giwano could signify a more intense fracturing of the basement in this zone.

Fig.3 Magnetic lineament map derived from anomaly 'closure' and 'nosing' of fig.2

Depth estimates from spectral analysis of magnetic data indicate a two depth source model. The depth of the deeper source range from 1900m to 2620m, this could be identified with basement. The shallow source range from 512m to 670m, this could be attributed to near surface intrusive and low-laying river valleys. The deeper depth Estimate are in agreement with those from gravity data over the upper Benue trough by (Osazuwa *et al* 1981).

Recently, exploration works for hydrocarbon began in the upper Benue trough. In the present study area, hydrocarbon prospects are largely doubtful because of the presence of basalt in the area whose emplacement may have destroyed geological traps.

Secondly, the high temperature that accompanied their emplacement may have converted any existing liquid hydrocarbon to gas. This could be lost by escape through fractures in the area.

Thirdly, depth estimates in the area generally low to favour hydrocarbon formation except in the NE section (Table 1 block 3) where the estimated depth is up to 2620m. This area is probably part of Shani sub-basin which adjoins the study area.

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